

2024-SCIENCE-BFSP, WP4

HARVEST: Handling and alignment of plant research FAIRification – value through the use of ELIXIR data Standards and Tools

D4.2: RDMkit pages updated and cross referenced on relevant websites

Tier: Science

Priority Area: Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens (BFSP)

Executive Summary

This deliverable focuses on updating and expanding the RDMKit Plant sciences page as a central hub for plant science research data management (RDM). The main outcome is the development of a comprehensive and cross-referenced resource that connects researchers with standards, tools, and guidelines. These updates ensure alignment with current best practices in FAIR data management and improve guidance on modern data packaging standards, metadata standards, data validation approaches, and data type-specific identifiers for reproducibility.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

ISA	Investigation S tudy A ssay Framework
RO-Crate	R esearch O bject C rate
ARC	A nnnotated R esearch C ontext
EVA	E uropean V ariation A rchive
MIAPPE	M inimum I nformation A bout P lant P henotyping E xperiments
MCPD	M ulti- C rop P assport D escriptors

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Update of relevant RDMkit pages

The Plant sciences page content was revised to reflect the most recent community updates and improvements made within the first work package. Documentation on plant data standards and tools was enriched, ensuring consistency with community best practices. See Pull request (<https://github.com/elixir-europe/rdmkit/pull/1724>) and the updated page (https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/plant_sciences)

Key improvements include:

- Enhanced documentation on reproducible data packaging formats, specifically:
 - ISA (Investigation-Study-Assay) framework
 - RO-Crate (Research Object Crate) for packaging research data
 - ARC (Annotated Research Context) for plant data management
- Clear instructions for describing experimental plant materials using MCPD (Multi-Crop Passport Descriptors) and MIAPPE Biological Material standards
- New guidance on variant identification best practices
- New comprehensive section on validation of plant phenotypic and genotypic data
- Updated recommendations for data sharing and publication

Update of websites to cross-reference RDMKit pages

As part of this deliverable, new reference links have been added or will be added to various resources:

- MIAPPE: <https://www.miappe.org/support/>
- Ro-Crate: https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/use_cases (pending)
- EVA ro-crate endpoint: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/eva/webservices/rest/swagger-ui.html#!/studies/getStudyRoCrateUsingGET> (pending)

Outcomes and expected impact

The RDMKit Plant sciences page is now comprehensively updated and cross-referenced with external websites, improving visibility and usability. Reciprocal links ensure that researchers can seamlessly navigate between RDMKit and standards-specific resources (MIAPPE, BrAPI, Bioschemas, FAIRsharing). Together, these efforts position RDMKit as the central, authoritative gateway for plant science RDM.

Dissemination Plans

The RDMKit update will be published on the RDMKit websites, and further dissemination is planned for the upcoming ELIXIR All Hands Meeting 2026.